

Affordances and constraints: a cybernetic interpretation

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Abstract

Affordances are possibilities that organisms can actualize, either in behavioral or evolutionary contexts. For example, an empty shell affords a home for the hermit crab *Pagurus bernhardus*, or feathers can become flight stabilizers, while originally carrying out the function of thermal insulators. Once a possibility is chosen, it becomes a constraint for the organisms, since it limits some actions or some features. At the same time, this constraint is also a window to a new space of opportunities, hence it is the source of further affordances. The interplay between affordances and constraints develops as a spiral in the evolution of the biosphere, in the development of behavior in animals, and also in social contexts such as music improvisation. In this contribution, we elaborate on the entangled link between affordances and constraints—and their role in the emergence of new properties in living systems—by discussing it in relation to the theory of self-organizing systems emerged in the second-order cybernetics and with the principle of organization established in the recent philosophy of biology.

1 Introduction

Species evolution and organism adaptation processes can be described at a high level in terms of a continuous interleaving between *affordances*—i.e. opportunities

for the organisms—and *constraints*—i.e. the actualization of one of the possibilities available to the organisms (Kauffman, 2016, 2019). Once an affordance is seized in evolution, or chosen in the adaptation process of an organism, it becomes a constraint that, in turn, creates new further affordances. This is often emphasized by making the enabling role of constraints explicit. The intertwined, co-dependent, and co-generative relation between affordances and constraints is in fact a kind of *Janus Bifrons*, as they establish both a conclusion and a new beginning (Ceruti, 1994).

The fundamental role of affordances for adaptation¹ has been elaborated and discussed also by highlighting the *unprestatability*² of affordances, which has to be ascribed to the properties of organismal agency and autonomy (Walsh, 2015; Moreno and Mossio, 2015; Roli et al., 2022; Jaeger, 2023).

Adaptive processes implicate the change of part of the organization of the systems involved. In evolution, the changes concern heritable variations, while modifications in the hierarchy of network processes composing the organization of the organism are typical of organism adaptation. These variations are often associated to the arising of new properties in the systems, which may consist of e.g. new phenotypic traits, new functions, new behaviors, new capacities.

In this paper, we elaborate on the relation between affordances and constraints, mainly in reference to cybernetic works on self-organizing systems. We believe that this provides a solid theoretical ground for detailing the main mechanisms, processes and properties involved. Moreover, the notion of biological organization, as discussed in the context of autopoiesis and in the recent developments of the philosophy of biology, especially in relation to the closure of constraints, completes this theoretical interpretation of the subject and makes it possible to explain the emergence of new systemic properties in a principled frame.

2 Affordances and constraints in adaptation

Affordances and constraints are an indissoluble combination of possibilities and choices, insofar as when a choice is made in the space of possibilities, a constraint is created, e.g. a relation or a limit in the use of a function. This constraint opens further new paths for affordances. In this section we discuss this fundamental dynamics in relation to evolutionary and organism adaptation processes.

The term “affordance” was introduced by Gibson (1966) referring to the perception of objects and situations by organisms in an environment that can afford them possible actions. These objects can either be inanimate structures, such as rocks, or other organisms. Actions are the activities undertaken by the organism in its environment and the functions performed to support its maintenance and ultimately its survival. For example, a hole in a trunk affords a squirrel a safe place to hide, or a shell affords a home for the hermit crab *Pagurus bernhardus*. Since the initial work by Gibson in ecological psychology, the notion of affordance has been elaborated in

¹Adaptation includes both processes involving individual organisms, and species evolution.

²A process is said to be *unprestatable* when the space of possibilities of its evolution cannot be predicted and therefore no probability can be defined on its evolutionary trajectories (Longo et al., 2012).

diverse fields, encompassing biosemiotics (Campbell et al., 2019), robotics (Jamone et al., 2016) and philosophy (Heras-Escribano, 2019).

Most adaptations in evolution relies on affordances, generally seized by heritable variation and natural selection. Prominent examples of seized affordances in evolution are exaptations (Gould and Vrba, 1982), whereby an organ is co-opted for performing a new function, as in the case of flight feathers, evolved for accomplishing functions such as thermal insulation and then used to stabilize flight (Prum and Brush, 2002), and of lens crystallins, which originated first as enzymes (Barve and Wagner, 2013). Besides gene mutations, heritable variations include also epigenetic phenomena (Jablonka and Lamb, 2002). For example, evolutionary adaptation can be achieved by organisms through *phenotypic plasticity*, in which adaptation occurs without requiring a genetic variation; this phenotypic variant can be inherited if produced by epigenetic differences in gene expressions (Thorson et al., 2017), or it can bias the subsequent selection of favourable genetic traits (West-Eberhard, 2005).

Affordances play a crucial role not only in evolution, but also in organism behavior and adaptation. Here affordances represent options for the actions an organism can take, which may also include learning. In this context, affordances are opportunities objects or situations offer to an agent for reaching its goals. Walsh (2015) points out that affordances are not independent features of an object, but they rather emerge from a triadic relation involving also the agent’s goals and repertoire of actions. This point is particularly important, since it is at the basis, on the one hand, of the notion of organismal agency, and, on the other hand, of the fact that affordances are *indefinite* and *unprestatable* (Kauffman and Roli, 2021; Roli et al., 2025).

As observed by Kull (2015), the act of choosing an action by an organism is triggered when a problem as to be faced, caused by “a situation of confusion, of logical conflict, incompatibility, inconsistency or contradiction”. This also holds for affordances, which can be driven by random events, accidents or by a change in the environment. Changes in the environment consist in any alteration that takes place in the portion of the world that the organism can perceive and with which it interacts. This niche represents the *umwelt* of the organism, according to von Uexküll (von Uexküll, 2010; Kull, 1998).

When an affordance is chosen—or seized—a choice is made by the system among the possible options available; in other terms, the system chooses one of the possibilities composing its *adjacent possible* (Kauffman, 2016). The adjacent possible is contingent and specific, for it is constituted of affordances which depend upon the goals and the repertoire of actions of the agent involved (Walsh, 2015). The act of choosing an affordance creates information, in that this choice breaks a symmetry because, among the indefinite affordances composing the adjacent possible, some are selected and therefore can be now distinguished (Roli et al., 2025). This introduces a difference among affordances, i.e. it is “the difference that makes the difference” (Bateson, 1972). Crucially, the choice of an affordance generates a constraint that, on the one hand, stabilizes the new condition and, on the other hand, expands the adjacent possible. For example, in the context of exaptations, when a new organ is selected for a new function, this becomes a constraint for the evolution of that species; however, at the same time, this enables the exploration of new possi-

bilities that are created by the new function performed by the organ. This process of continuous choice and creation of opportunities can be visualized as a growing spiral process. The constraints that arise from seized affordances stabilize a new state of the process or support certain dynamics within it, while also opening up additional possibilities. These resulting constraints are in fact *enabling constraints* (Kauffman, 2016). A cultural analogy to this process is that of music improvisation (Roli, 2022), for example in jazz music: the substitution of a chord with another one produces new harmonic options. That particular substitution was possible because of the history of the previous states of the music execution, i.e. that chord substitution was in the adjacent possible of harmonic choices before being executed. Once performed, the new chord becomes a constraint on the continuation of the piece of music; however, it also opens further new possibilities that did not exist before the chord substitution.

In the following section, we propose an interpretation from the standpoint of cybernetics elaborations of the notion of self-organized systems by means of information theory. Subsequently, we combine this interpretation with the notion of biological organization. We believe this may provide a formal description of the tangled interplay between affordances and constraints that contributes to clarifying this dynamics and provides a ground to explain its role in the emergence of new properties in complex systems.

3 A cybernetic interpretation

We consider the case of open systems far from equilibrium. These systems exchange energy and matter with their environment, and are subject to perturbations. To maintain themselves coherent they need to compensate external perturbations and, in case, rearrange their structure to adapt to external changing conditions. Ashby (1956) observes that these characteristics make these systems capable of undergoing self-organization. According to Ashby (1954), these systems are adaptive in the sense that they are either able to immediately respond to external perturbation or to rearrange some parts of their structure so as to cope with perturbations and maintain their essential variables in vital ranges (i.e. to keep homeostasis). In the context of biological organisms, the former case presupposes that an evolutionary adaptation had taken place to provide the organisms the repertoire behaviors useful to react to external stimuli. This aspect will be discussed in Section 4 in the context of the notion of biological organization. Here we focus on the works by von Foerster and Atlan in which a formalization of adaptation is provided in terms of information theory.

When a system³ is capable of adaptation, then it is subject to internal modifications (consisting either in individual development or evolutionary variations). As the system maintains its operative conditions in spite of external perturbations, its internal order is supposed to increase, meaning that whenever an adaptation event occurs, new functions appear and new constraints (relations, regularities, etc.) are

³We generically write *system*, even if we are referring to biological organisms and super-organisms.

formed. In information theory formalism, this can be stated as an increase of *redundancy* (von Foerster, 2003). It is important to observe that the term *redundancy* is not solely used in reference to duplication of structures, but also—and mainly—to regularities and alternative paths for achieving a certain function.⁴ Using information theory (Shannon, 1948), the redundancy of a system is defined as:

$$R = 1 - \frac{H}{H_m} \quad (1)$$

whereby H is the entropy of an information source and H_m its maximal entropy value. While this definition is based on the transmission of a message from a source to a destination via a communication channel, the meaning of system entropy can be provided in reference to its internal content, considering both structural and functional elements. H (resp. H_m) is therefore the entropy (resp. maximal entropy) of its description with respect to an observer (von Foerster, 2003; Atlan, 1974). Since redundancy refers to the organized part of the system expressed as constraints (representing structural and functional regularities, limitations, invariants, and relations), H_m is the entropy of the system considered without any constraint (Atlan, 1974). From Equation 1, we derive that $R = 1$ when its description is maximally regular ($H = 0$), while $R = 0$ when the system is totally lacking regularities.

The variables involved in Equation 1 have an implicit dependence on time; therefore, they should all be considered as quantities subject to change in time. Hence, the variation of R can be expressed as:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = -\frac{H_m \frac{dH}{dt} - H \frac{dH_m}{dt}}{H_m^2} \quad (2)$$

If we assume that in self-organizing systems R increases in time (von Foerster, 2003), we obtain:

$$H \frac{dH_m}{dt} > H_m \frac{dH}{dt} \quad (3)$$

We can distinguish two special cases in Equation 3:

- (a) $H = \text{const} \Rightarrow \frac{dH_m}{dt} > 0$
- (b) $H_m = \text{const} \Rightarrow \frac{dH}{dt} < 0$

These cases show that, if R increases in time H_m must increase to keep the same entropy of the system and, if H_m does not change, H decreases. In general, given a message on an alphabet with N symbols, the maximal entropy of the message can be $\log_2 N$. In our case, the number of symbols corresponds to structural and functional elements of the system. Therefore, if constraints are added to the system, then its entropy (i.e. the description of its organization) decreases unless more “elements” are added, so as to increase also H_m . If this does not happen, then the system is gradually drifted towards a completely regular condition, characterized by $H = 0$. We may say that it moves toward a crystal state (Atlan, 1979).

⁴This property is also named *degeneracy* (Edelman and Gally, 2001).

As observed in Section 2, living complex systems that undergo adaptation (both individual and evolutionary) are continuously experiencing the cycle affordance–constraint and therefore, from a cybernetic viewpoint, they increase redundancy. Nevertheless, we commonly observe that the complexity of organisms grows in time, insofar as they acquire capabilities, functions, processes and structures useful for their survival. When this happens, also entropy H increases. As a consequence, H_m must increase as well. Indeed, H_m increases because of two main reasons: *i.* the choice of a possibility creates information and hence, it introduces new symbols, and *ii.* the new constraint does not only augments R , but it also opens new possibilities. We can see this effect from an alternative perspective by rewriting Equation 2 with H as a function of R and H_m (Atlan, 1974, 1979):

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = -H_m \frac{dR}{dt} + (1 - R) \frac{H_m}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 highlights the fact that, for H to grow (or at least not to decrease) despite an increase of R , H_m must increase.

The role played by constraints in increasing R is fundamental. In the following section, the notion has to be clarified and defined in the context of theoretical biology.

4 Biological organization

A coherent and well-founded account of biological organization is provided by *autopoiesis* (Maturana and Varela, 1972; Varela et al., 1974; Varela, 1979). It worth to remark that autopoiesis explicitly motivates the need for an organism to counter-balance external perturbations, also in the form of deterioration. According to this view, organisms can “make themselves” and keep their own identity and coherence. This is achieved by operational closure of the internal processes of the organisms. Quoting Varela (1979): “Autonomous systems are mechanistic (dynamic) systems defined as a unity by their organization. We shall say that autonomous systems are organizationally closed. That is, their organization is characterized by processes such that (1) the processes are related as a network, so that they recursively depend on each other in the generation and realization of the processes themselves, and (2) they constitute the system as a unity recognizable in the space (domain) in which the processes exist.”

The notion of closure is more precisely defined and elaborated by Montévil and Mossio (2015), with the *closure of constraints*. In thermodynamic processes, work is produced by constraining energy into few degrees of freedom (Kauffman, 2000). Yet, constraints are built through work. Therefore, we consider systems composed of processes that can take place under certain constraints, which in turn need to be produced. The notion of constraint in the organization of biological organisms is wider than that of constraint in thermodynamics. Constraints play the role of structures that enable the execution of a process; they can be in the form e.g. of boundary conditions, parameters, restrictions on the configuration space, stable relations between components (Mossio et al., 2016). They represent the main regular part inside the organisms because they exert conditions on the processes such that they are carried

out properly (i.e. they accomplish a specific task or function). Therefore, they can be captured by redundancy, as defined in Section 3.

More formally, let's consider a process that produces B from the transformation of A and whose execution is constrained by constraint C_1 ; we can write $C(A \rightarrow B)$, making the constraint explicit. As constraints are in turn produced by processes, in the system there exists a process creating also C_1 , for example $C_2(Z \rightarrow C_1)$. The closure of constraints prescribes a regime of causation, in which the constraints have a loop dependence. Formally, a set of constraints $\mathcal{C} = \{C_1, \dots, C_i, \dots, C_n\}$ is a closure if, for each $C_i \in \mathcal{C}$:

1. C_i depends directly on at least one other constraint $C_j \in \mathcal{C}$, with $i \neq j$; and
2. there is at least one constraint $C_k \in \mathcal{C}$ such that C_k depends on C_i .

The closure of constraints is crucial for the organisms since “[i]n a general sense, dependence between constraints underlies any repair mechanisms at work in the organism” (Mossio et al., 2016, p.30). Remarkably, it is also at the core of the process of recognizing and choosing affordances in organisms, because the closure of constraint provides the functions that an organism can apply (i.e. the repertoire of actions), it is contextual to the specific organism (supporting organismal agency), and it produces reactions to external perturbations such that it is preserved. Moreover, it can also change in time (Montévil et al., 2016) as a response to external stimuli: “closure, in the relevant situations, favors and enhances functional variation, i.e. variation of the organization itself” (Mossio et al., 2016, p.31). The same concept can be expressed in terms of affordances, constraints and the adjacent possible: new constraints can be added to the closure (and other can disappear from it) as the result of the choice of an opportunity in the adjacent possible.

5 Conclusion

In this contribution we have proposed a grounded theoretical framework for the interpretation of the interplay between affordances and constraints in adaptation processes, both concerning individual organisms and species evolution. A cybernetics perspective focusing on information theory provides formal principles to define this creative dynamics. A conceptual complement is offered by the theory of biological organization in terms of closure of constraints, where the notion of constraints is more precisely defined in reference to autopoietic systems.

This work is a first step in the attempt of revisiting principles arisen in the cybernetic studies (mainly in the second-order cybernetics) that can provide significant contributions to system science and philosophy of science in the fields of complex systems and biology.

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